

Synthesis and biological activity of thiazolo[3',2' : 2,3]-as-triazino[5,6-*b*]indoles and isomeric thiazolo[2',3' : 3,4]-as-triazino[5,6-*b*]indoles

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Abstract : 9/7-Bromo-2,3-dihydro-8-methoxy-5*H*-as-triazino[5,6-*b*]indole-3-thiones **3a,b** on condensation with 4-chlorophenacyl bromide give 9/7-bromo-3-[4-chlorophenylthio]-8-methoxy-5*H*-as-triazino[5,6-*b*]indole hydrobromides **4a,b** which on PPA catalysed cyclization furnish 6/8-bromo-3-[4-chlorophenyl-7-methoxythiazolo[3',2' : 2,3]-as-triazino[5,6-*b*]indoles **9a,b** and not angular isomeric 6/8-bromo-1-[4-chlorophenyl]-7-methoxythiazolo[2',3' : 3,4]-as-triazino[5,6-*b*]indoles **6a,b**. The unequivocal synthesis of the latter have also been accomplished. The antimicrobial potential of the compounds **6** and **9** have also been evaluated.

Keywords : Indoles, cyclization, antimicrobial activity, unequivocal synthesis.

Introduction

In continuation of our work¹⁻³ on biologically active heterocyclic compounds, we report herein the synthesis of isomeric condensed bridgehead nitrogen heterocyclic systems derived from unsymmetrical azine (mercaptoindolotriazine) and the antimicrobial potential associated with them. The structures of the compounds have been confirmed by means of elemental analysis and spectral data (IR and PMR).

Results and discussion

9/7-Bromo-2,3-dihydro-8-methoxy-5*H*-as-triazino[5,6-*b*]indole-3-thiones **3a,b** were obtained by the condensation of 4/6-bromo-5-methoxyisatins **1a,b** with thiosemicarbazide followed by cyclization of the intermediates 4/6-bromo-5-methoxy-3-thiosemicarbazones **2a,b** with alkali. When condensed with 4-chlorophenacyl bromide, **3a,b** gave 9/7-bromo-3-[4-chlorophenylthio]-8-methoxy-5*H*-as-triazino[5,6-*b*]indole hydrobromides **4a,b**. Being unsymmetrical the ketones **4a,b** on cyclization with PPA were expected to furnish 6/8-bromo-3-[4-chlorophenyl]-7-methoxythiazolo[3',2' : 2,3]-as-triazino[5,6-*b*]indoles **9a,b** or 6/8-bromo-1-[4-

chlorophenyl]-7-methoxythiazolo[2',3' : 3,4]-as-triazino[5,6-*b*]indoles **6a,b** or both depending upon the mode of cyclization (Scheme 1). However, cyclization of **4a,b** gave a single product (TLC), also confirmed by IR and PMR spectral data. The ketones **4a,b** exhibited a band at 1694/1696 cm⁻¹ (C=O) whereas absence of this band in the IR spectrum of **9a,b** showed the absence of carbonyl group, thereby suggesting cyclic structure for **9a,b**. The signals at δ 8.20/8.15 (1H, s, C₂-H) in the PMR structure of **6a,b** corroborated the cyclic structures. However, the spectral data were not of much help in deciding either the linear structure **9a,b** or the angular structure **6a,b** for the products.

The mode of cyclization in **4a,b** will be governed by the stability of transition state (**7** or **8**). In structures **4a,b**, N-4, being more nucleophilic than N-2 which are directly attached to N-1, will attack the carbonyl carbon of the ketones giving **7a,b**⁴. There exists a steric repulsion between NH of the pyrrole ring and aryl moiety of the keto-sulphide chain in **7a,b** and this crowding would render the transition state **7a,b** comparatively unstable. Thus the initially formed intermediates **7a,b** being energetically more active, open up and close at

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Scheme 1

N-2 to give energetically more favourable intermediates **8a,b** in which there would be no such steric crowding. These intermediates **8a,b** finally undergo prototropic change followed by loss of water molecule to give **9a,b**.

The unequivocal synthesis of the angular isomers **6a,b** was achieved by condensation of **2a,b** with 4-chlorophenacyl bromide followed by cyclization in the presence of POCl₃. The amide carbonyl (>N-C=O) absorptions at 1700/1705 cm⁻¹ in **5a,b** were found to be absent in the IR spectrum of **6a,b**. Further confirmation of the cyclic structures of **6a,b** forthcame from PMR spectra (vide Experimental).

The compounds **6a,b** and **9a,b** were screened for *in vitro* antifungal and antibacterial activity against pathogenic fungi [*Candida albicans* (CA), *Cryptococcus neoformans* (CN), *Sporotrichum schenckii* (SS), *Trichophyton mentagrophytes* (TM), *Aspergillus fumigatus* (AF)] and pathogenic bacteria [*Streptococcus faecalis* (SF), *Klebsiella pneumoniae* (KP), *Escherichia coli* (EC), *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (PA), *Staphylococcus aureus* (SA) penicillin resistance (2500 units)]. Compounds **6a,b** showed MIC 50 and 25 µg/ml against CN, SS, PA, SA and TM respectively, while **9a,b** showed MIC 50 and 25 µg/ml against SS, KP, EC, CA and TM respectively. The compounds were tested at 100 µg/ml concentration in DMSO by macrobroth two fold serial dilution technique. Amoxycyclin ketoconazole were used as standard for antibacterial and antifungal activity.

Experimental

Melting points were taken in open capillaries in sulphuric acid bath and are uncorrected. IR spectra were recorded in KBr on Perkin-Elmer IR spectrophotometer and PMR on Varian VXR-200 MHz spectrometer, using CDCl₃ as solvent. TMS was taken as internal standard. Chemical shifts are expressed in δ ppm. Purity of the compounds was checked by TLC silica gel G plates and spots were located by exposure to iodine vapours.

4-Bromo-5-methoxy-3-thiosemicarbazone **2a** :

A mixture of 4-bromo-5-methoxyisatin (0.01 mol), thiosemicarbazide (0.01 mol) and 2-3 drops of gl. acetic acid in ethanol (50 ml) was refluxed for 2 h, cooled to room temperature and the solid filtered, washed with methanol and dried. Yield 52%, m.p. > 250 °C, IR (cm⁻¹) : 586 (C-Br), 1135 (C=S), 1622 (C=N), 1686 (C=O), 3287, 3356, 3470 (NH, NH₂) (Found : C, 36.40; H, 2.70; N, 17.00. Calcd. for C₁₀H₉BrN₄O₂S : C, 36.47; H, 2.73; N, 17.02%). **2b** : Yield 50%, m.p. > 250 °C, IR (cm⁻¹) : 586 (C-Br), 1135 (C=S), 1622 (C=N), 1688

(C=O), 3285, 3356, 3466 (NH, NH₂) (Found : C, 36.42; H, 2.68; N, 17.98. Calcd. for C₁₀H₉BrN₄O₂S : C, 36.47; H, 2.73; N, 17.02%).

9-Bromo-2,3-dihydro-8-methoxy-5H-as-triazino[5,6-*b*]indole-3-thione **3a** :

It was obtained by base catalysed cyclization of **2a** according to method of Ram *et al.*⁵. Yield 62%, m.p. > 250 °C. IR (cm⁻¹) : 586 (C-Br), 1137 (C=S), 1560 (C-N stretching), 1635 (C=N), 3345 (NH) (Found : C, 38.43; H, 2.21; N, 17.98. Calcd. for C₁₀H₇BrN₄OS : C, 38.48; H, 2.25; N, 18.00%). **3b** : Yield 50%, m.p. > 250 °C, IR (cm⁻¹) : 586 (C-Br), 1135 (C=S), 1560 (C-N stretching), 1638 (C=N), 3345 (NH) (Found : C, 38.41; H, 2.21; N, 17.98. Calcd. for C₁₀H₇BrN₄OS : C, 38.48; H, 2.25; N, 18.00%).

9-Bromo-3-[4-chlorophenacylthio]-8-methoxy-5H-as-triazino[5,6-*b*]indole hydrobromide **4a** :

A mixture of **3a** (0.01 mol) and 4-chlorophenacyl bromide (0.01 mol) in DMF (50 ml) was heated under reflux for 5 h, cooled to room temperature and poured on crushed ice. The solid thus separated was filtered, washed with water and recrystallised from aq. DMF. Yield 42%, m.p. > 250 °C, IR (cm⁻¹) : 586 (C-Br), 768 (C-Cl), 1585 (C-N stretching), 1620 (C=N), 1694 (C=O), 3360 (NH) (Found : C, 38.92; H, 2.31; N, 10.08. Calcd. for C₁₈H₁₃Br₂ClN₄O₂S : C, 38.98; H, 2.34; N, 10.10%). **4b** : Yield 50%, m.p. > 250 °C, IR (cm⁻¹) : 586 (C-Br), 768 (C-Cl), 1585 (C-N stretching), 1622 (C=N), 1696 (C=O), 3360 (NH) (Found : C, 38.92; H, 2.30; N, 10.02. Calcd. for C₁₈H₁₃Br₂ClN₄O₂S : C, 38.98; H, 2.34; N, 10.10%).

6-Bromo-3-[4-chlorophenyl]-7-methoxythiazolo[3',2' : 2,3]-as-triazino[5,6-*b*]indole **9a** :

Compound **4a** (0.01 mol) in PPA (10 ml) was heated in an oil bath at 140-150 °C for 5 h. The reaction mixture was cooled to room temperature, poured in ice-cold water and neutralised with aq. K₂CO₃ solution. The solid thus separated was filtered, washed with water and recrystallised from aq. DMF. Yield 71%, m.p. 260 °C, IR (cm⁻¹) : 586 (C-Br), 768 (C-Cl), 1520 (C-N stretching), 1621 (C=N), PMR : 3.39 (3H, s, OMe), 7.11-7.92 (6H, m, aromatic protons), 7.99 (1H, s, C₂-H) (Found : C, 48.49; H, 2.20; N, 12.56. Calcd. for C₁₈H₁₀BrClN₄OS : C, 48.53; H, 2.24; N, 12.58%). **9b** : Yield 70%, 258 °C, IR (cm⁻¹) : 586 (C-Br), 768 (C-Cl), 1520 (C-N stretching), 1620 (C=N), PMR : 3.36 (3H, s, OMe), 7.15-8.00 (6H, m, aromatic protons), 8.05 (1H, s, C₂-H) (Found : C, 48.49; H, 2.22; N, 12.53. Calcd. for C₁₈H₁₀BrClN₄OS : C, 48.53; H, 2.24; N, 12.58%).

4-Bromo-5-methoxy-3-[(4-chlorophenyl)-2'-thiazolyl]-hydrozonohydrobromide 5a :

A mixture of **2a** (0.01 mol) and 4-chlorophenacyl bromide (0.01 mol) in anhyd. ethanol (25 ml) and DMF (25 ml) was heated under reflux for 4 h. The reaction mixture was concentrated, cooled to room temperature and poured into ice-cold water and the solid was filtered, washed with water and recrystallised from aq. DMF. Yield 39%, m.p. 239 °C, IR (cm⁻¹) : 586 (C-Br), 768 (C-Cl), 1538 (C-N stretching), 1600, 1620 (C=C and C=N), 1700 (>N-C=O), 3290 (NH) (Found : C, 38.95; H, 2.30; N, 10.07. Calcd. for C₁₈H₁₃Br₂ClN₂O₂S : C, 38.98; H, 2.34; N, 10.10%). **5b** : Yield 40%, m.p. 235 °C, IR (cm⁻¹) : 586 (C-Br), 768 (C-Cl), 1538 (C-N stretching), 1600, 1620 (C=C and C=N), 1705 (>N-C=O), 3290 (NH) (Found : C, 38.90; H, 2.30; N, 10.07. Calcd. for C₁₈H₁₃Br₂ClN₂O₂S : C, 38.98; H, 2.34; N, 10.10%).

6-Bromo-1-[4-chlorophenyl]-7-methoxythiazolo[2',3':3,4]-as-triazino[5,6-b]indole 6a :

Compound **5a** (0.01 mol) in POCl₃ (15 ml) was heated in oil bath at 120–130 °C for 3 h. The reaction mixture was cooled to room temperature, poured into cold water and neutralised with aq. K₂CO₃ solution. The solid, thus separated was filtered, washed with water and recrystallised from aq. DMF. Yield 68%, m.p. >250 °C, IR (cm⁻¹) : 586 (C-Br), 768 (C-Cl), 1536 (C-N

stretching), 1622 (C=N), PMR : 3.50 (3H, s, OMe), 7.20–7.80 (6H, m, aromatic protons), 8.20 (1H, s, C₂-H) (Found : C, 48.50; H, 2.21; N, 12.56. Calcd. for C₁₈H₁₀BrClN₄OS : C, 48.53; H, 2.24; N, 12.58%). **6b** : Yield 64%, m.p. >250 °C, IR (cm⁻¹) : 586 (C-Br), 768 (C-Cl), 1536 (C-N stretching), 1622 (C=N), PMR : 3.39 (3H, s, OMe), 7.10–7.88 (6H, m, aromatic protons), 8.10 (1H, s, C₂-H) (Found : C, 48.50; H, 2.20; N, 12.55. Calcd. for C₁₈H₁₀BrClN₄OS : C, 48.53; H, 2.24; N, 12.58%).

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